

CULTUROLOGY

CULTURAL SELF-IDENTIFICATION OF THE KAZAKH PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the article is to justify that cultural identification is a process of unity (identification) of a person with cultural ideals, historically developed in the national culture of the state (country) on the basis of spiritual values, preserved and transmitted to descendants by the spiritual teacher as a national treasure.

Such a fundamental concept of the moral renewal of the Kazakh people at the turn of the 19th-20th centuries was the teaching of Abai “Be a human!”. This concept arises from a person’s need for comprehension, awareness of his spiritual connection with the world for self-realization.

Everyone needs it, since not a single person can do without ideas and ideas that express his attitude to his environment to himself.

The article substantiates the idea that the moral concept of Abai “Be a human!” there is an expression of extremely general grounds for self-identification and aims at the fundamental characteristic of human being.

Abai, at the crossroads of East and West cultures, at the same time perceived their spiritual and moral values. However, he was not only the interpreter (adapter) of these cultures: on their basis he developed a different synthetic image of the world and the presence of man in it. If in the West the thesis “change of the world” dominated, and in the East – the knowledge of oneself as part of nature, then Abai formed the imperative “Be (become) a human (man)!” as a philosophical concept. The greatness of the phenomenal genius of Abai was expressed in the fact that in his socio-philosophical lyrics, contrary to all the “abominations of being” and the tragedy of fate, he raised the stamina of the human spirit to an unprecedented height, implanted the hope of a better life in the minds of his contemporaries.

Keywords: Abai, self-identification, human ideal, enlightenment, human qualities, the meaning of being.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of “identity”, generic in relation to self-identification, is given the following definition in the normative literature: “The term identity is applied to many political, social, ethnic and cultural phenomena, its general content is the identity of the object with itself, its existence within clear boundaries, the certainty of its being, relative immutability, movable stability, integrity. Identity can also be understood as a developed state of an object, in evaluative categories - a desired state” [Concept, 1996]. By the way, it is curious that a seemingly purely philosophical concept was included in the political document: this clearly characterizes the urgency of this problem. This problem is becoming one of the most urgent today, including for Kazakhstani science and public practice [Malinin, 1999, 41]. If we take the point of view of the formational approach, then it should be recognized that culture is in a constant process of development, but, therefore, in fact, its constancy does not exist, i.e. a strong self-identity. It should be noted that the imperative of Abai “Be a human!” universal and addressed to the human race as a whole, and not only to the Kazakh people. “We would tirelessly expand the circle of our interests, multiply the knowledge that feed our souls. We would understand

that the blessings of the soul are incomparably higher than the bodily ones and subordinate the carnal needs to the dictates of the soul” - this is how Abai considered the imperative “Become a man!” [Abai, 1993].

Abai's imperative “Be (become) a man (human)”, as a philosophical concept, contains in a reduced form a specific formula for the formation of the human principle in a person, since it reflects the essence and purpose of a person in the world, and is not a simple didactic commandment: “be like that or another figure”. This path of becoming human in a person is a long process that breaks down into periods that coincide with the stages of socialization of the individual. The process, as a result of which, on the one hand, occurs the interiorization (internalization) of social norms, moral principles, that is, the conversion of a person into a personality. On the other hand, there is also a reverse process - exteriorization, i.e. individual qualities are socialized, negative personality traits are overcome and socially significant, “universal” ones are established. Only on the path of self-knowledge and self-education does a person achieve inner perfection, acquire truly human qualities. But this path is not easy and thorny. Throughout his life, a person has to constantly become himself, reproduce moral qualities in actions and deeds

and overcome negative qualities. Abai's reflections on a perfect, highly moral personality found the fullest expression in his ethical concept "Be a human!". The structure of the concept includes two main aspects:

1) All that should not be done in order to become a human: What qualities of character, according to Abai, are destructive for a person? These are pride, passion, envy, arrogance, lies, laziness, greed, hatred, cruelty and other moral negatives. They lead the human heart to callousness and cruelty, and it becomes insensitive. A person must cleanse himself of them. It is necessary to avoid such disgusting qualities as: slander, lies, boasting, idleness and extravagance [Abai, 1954, 63]. Without overcoming these vices, a person is not able to achieve cultural and moral perfection.

2) All that should be done in order to become, to be human: initially to develop in oneself sincerity, hard work, philanthropy, mercy, compassion, charity, moderation, truthfulness, kindness, modesty, justice, that is, those qualities that induce a person for improvement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The article uses the method of comparative analysis of identification processes in the spiritual space of Central Asia in the 19th-21st centuries in the context of the ideas of Abai Kunanbayev. The analysis was based not only on philosophical sources, but also on sources of other areas of knowledge, primarily of literary, historical and cultural, as well as cultural and ethnographic order.

Comparative methodology (comparison, analogy, juxtaposition, dialogue, parallelism) based on the development of a system of criteria for self-identification of a Kazakh person at the turn of the century allows us to consider them as parts of a single whole. It is philosophical comparative studies that allows us to touch upon the "deep layers" of culture, which makes it possible to comprehend one culture through the prism of another, which is characteristic of Abai. This method was widely used by Abai to compare the ideas of Russian (Western) and Eastern spirituality. As a theoretical and methodological approach, the article uses a cross-cultural intertemporal "cross-time" analysis, which made it possible to compare the indicators and characteristics of two traditional cultures in temporal dimension and dynamics. At the same time, the article uses logical-historical, axiological approaches. Additional methods were the method of systems analysis and hermeneutics. The key moments, firstly, were the ideas about the picture of the world, expressed in folk legends and beliefs, traditions, customs, rituals, etc., which are the basis of Abai's worldview.

The ethical meaning of the imperative "Be a human!" consists in a moral assessment of the role and purpose of a person in society. People should contain a synthetic unity of reason and humanity, hard work and education, friendship and love. A genuine (full-fledged) person must instill, cultivate positive qualities in himself, find his place in life. The imperative "Be a human" includes a system of requirements, the fulfillment of which is a guarantee of perfection and authenticity. According to Abai, a perfect person should be active, honestly work, strive for knowledge, rationality in actions, be benevolent, fight evil, be conscientious.

These moral requirements are complex; they must be transformed into conscious desires, into the life principles of people. As norms of public morality, they must turn into real actions and deeds, into everyday human behavior. What traits can unite different cultures scattered in time and space? In other words, is there something in common between cultures that are distant from each other for thousands of years of human history, between the cultures of different peoples existing in the same historical era, but significantly different from each other both as a result of the natural conditions of their life and as a result of a significant gap in the level of development of productive forces, science, education, etc. At the same time, as rightly noted, something essentially common, inherent in culture as a specifically human activity and its objective and institutional objectification, is exactly what makes a person a person [Kurganskaya, 2003, 59-60].

In addition, and this is the most important for us in this case, culture itself can be considered as the broadest cultural universal [Dramaliev, 1990, 110-113]. Indeed, wherever a person appears, he is always followed by culture as a specific human activity. It is obvious that culture is also a specific feature of a person.

The imperative "Be (become) a human" is directed not only outside, for others, as moral didactics, but also inside, as a means of self-realization, i.e. has a moral side, because it recognizes the freedom of the subject to act in accordance with his conviction [Abai, 1993, 63].

The logic of Abai's thought inevitably leads to the conclusion: a person must turn inside himself, look for grounds for choosing a line of behavior in order to become a real, "full-fledged" person. This means the recognition of the personal principle of moral life and presupposes the conscious and responsible behavior of a person.

The ethical categories highlighted by Abai (conscience, shame, duty, honor, justice, etc.) and philosophies were developed on the basis of a person's practical orientation in the world, and therefore have national features, characterize the originality of the thinking of the Kazakh people, emphasize its specifics.

One of the features of Abai's humanistic methodology is that the means of knowledge, moral ideals are not given to a person in a ready-made form and do not exist independently of him. They are potentially built into human nature, presented in the form of a "project" that a person has to realize (translation of the mind in potency, first, into the actual, then into the acquired, as in the teachings of al-Farabi about the soul). In the 19th Word, Abai expounds this idea as follows: "A child is not born a reasonable being. It is only by listening and watching, examining everything by touching and tasting, that is learns what is good and what is bad. The more a child sees and hears, the more it knows. One may learn a good deal by listening to wise men. It is not enough to be endowed with a brain – only by hearing and memorizing the teachings of the learnt and by avoiding vices one can grow up a complete person" [Abai, 2005, 114].

Human life is a social activity in which personal contacts, relationships, collective rapprochement and connections of people arise and are formed to achieve

the set goal. Moral activity in this aspect is social in the broad sense of the word. Moral relations are not invented by man, they hover in the spiritual structure of being as objective real relations of people. This is of particular importance for Kazakhs. The spiritual aspect of civilization turned out to be immeasurably more important for them than the factors of material production. Neither the economic nor the political aspects of society can fulfill the role of the keeper and translator of historical memory, which the spiritual structure of civilization successfully fulfills. Interpersonal relationships in Kazakh culture are so fundamental that they form the entire system of spiritual production. Special spiritual relationships are natural in this society "and constitute a kind of communication code, language and method of communication, as well as the form of transmission of symbols. The social carriers of this civilization ensure its integrity, which appears as a unity of spiritual values, ideas, knowledge, orientation, norms and symbols" [Orynbekov, 1995, 29].

Abai described this problem in detail in the 38th Word. From a humanistic standpoint, Abai, for the first time in the history of his people, raised a cardinal question - what should be the appearance of a genuine person - which can radically change the cultural and moral content of society, educate its people in the spirit of humanism. "It is a sacred duty of each of us to increase the number of our friends. This depends on our good will and warmth of heart towards other people, something that must evoke a response in kind. At least do not wish ill to others, do not try to put ourselves above them by your words or deeds". [Abai, 2005, 163].

Society must create the necessary conditions, help a person find himself. A two-pronged process is seen here: the active work of a person on himself and social determinants that affect a person from the outside. Both can not be successfully carried out without purposeful human activity, labor efforts, awareness of the social significance of labor as a vital need and as the basis of morality.

Abai believed in the possibility of changing the social environment, believed in the possibility of re-educating individuals through enlightenment, in the spirit of humanism. Therefore, his concept of a harmonious, moral personality contains deep thoughts and constructive ideas. The idea of the decisive role of labor in the moral formation of a person is constantly present in the ethical concept of Abai. Diligence is the beginning of morality, and man, work is the true bearer of virtue, therefore Abai calls people who live honest labor "holy people" [Abai, 1954, 338].

The moral impact of labor on the formation of a person also lies in the fact that, according to Abai, labor is the main means of ridding people of vices. If people constantly work in society, then such vices as the habit of idle life, parasitism, laziness, etc. will disappear. [Abai, 1954, 400].

Thus, Abai's belief in the transformative role of labor is one of the sources of universal human values, following which a person discovers a full-fledged being in himself. One of the necessary conditions for the implementation of the moral imperative "Become a human!" as a philosophical concept and, at the same time, one of

the main duties of a person, along with hard work, Abai considered the striving for knowledge, for rationality, making the moral qualities of a person dependent on intellectual development, on the maturity of the mind. Abai recreates the original model of a perfect person, which is characterized by the following qualities: activity, work, high aspirations, creative thinking, a sense of beauty. Become a Human Concept - there is a path on which a person does good by actions, thoughts, feelings - this path leads to a perfect personality, the properties of which are a bright mind and the burning heart.

A perfect person is a highly moral, virtuous person. Such moral qualities are acquired by him in the process of thoughtful and systematic educational work and become a necessary state of the soul, which regulates the conditions of genuine human existence.

Abai proves that a "full-fledged person" must have the following qualities: have a burning heart and have a bright mind, love the truth, hate lies, have a proud soul and value honor, strive for spiritual perfection, despise material goods, be fair.

As Abai believed, the true, authentic essence of a perfect person is not external, which is perceived by the senses, but internal - comprehended by the mind. The inner world, inner perfection, Abai defined as the unity of goodness and beauty, moral principles of man. "The dignity of a person," writes Abai, "is determined not by appearance and wealth..., but by heart and mind" [Abai, 1993, 131].

Each era solved the problem of man in its own way, only now it has acquired special acuteness in connection with the negatives of the process of globalization of public life. Nowadays, when the situation of ubiquitous excessive egoism, both individual and group, prevails in the world, a person must develop a radically different way of being in the world. Such a way of being, in which the task of human development and improvement would be resolved, is inextricably linked with the establishment of spiritual and moral values in society. Hence, there arises an urgent need to refer to the history of philosophical and ethical thought, where the main ideas that reveal the human in man are concentrated. The most important component of Abai's philosophical views is the doctrine of morality, closely related to the problems of the formation of a moral personality and aimed at the humanistic education of both an individual and society as a whole.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

As one of the researchers of Abai's creativity M.O. Auezov: "...the majority of Abai's philosophical views rest on the problem of humanity" [Auezov, 1995, 18]. Abai inherits and develops the ideas of the thinkers of the East, al-Ghazali, Ibn Tfeil, Omar Khayama, Nizami, Savadzhi, Ferdowsi, Saadi) who asserted that humanity is the basis of human life, its creative daring, striving for the future. This is how Nizami instructed: "If a person, so know, you are with people, perceive their intelligence and humanity", and in Salmon Savadzhi (1300-1375) we find the following statement: "He is a person in whose heart is kindness" [Karpyk, 1995, 83-84].

Abai's principle "Be a human" as the main way of self-identification of a person is widely discussed in

modern Kazakhstan. To classify all the variety of identification strategies-programs existing in Kazakhstani society, a number of grounds-criteria are required. They are put forward in his works, for example, by G.V. Malinin: in relation to the past, according to the degree of ethnicity, according to the nature of the distribution of property and power in society, in relation to the national state structure, according to the correlation of strategies-projects with the global civilization process [Malinin, 1997, 26].

In addition, G.V. Malinin distinguishes three levels of self-identification: 1) the macro level, where Kazakhstan is identified in geopolitical and regional terms; 2) the average level of self-identification, which consists in self-determination of oneself as a state organized community, the acquisition of national unity and the corresponding identity; 3) micro level of self-identification, i.e. self-determination of individuals in relation to local identities, i.e. communities based on monogenism (confessional, ethnic, etc.) and characterized by solidarity between their members [Malinin, 1999, 41].

To this, obviously, it should be added that the types of identity must be distinguished not only, so to speak, "horizontally", but also "vertically". In the personal positioning system, the landmarks of the national and civilizational plan constitute only one of the levels of identification, and not always the main one; ethnic and ethnocultural, religious, ideological, political and other vectors of identity also received the opportunity for free development [Semenenko, 2004, 101-114]. The correlation of cultural identity with other types of identity: social, ethnic, civic, etc. looks the same. [Yadov, 1994, 38].

The high appraisal of the role of labor as the main strategy for human self-realization found a response from his descendants. The thinker believed that the most important condition and means of self-realization of a true person is work, activity. According to Abai, attitude to work is the main, objective measure of the moral essence of an individual. A genuine person relies on his work, which is a condition for his well-being and freedom, idleness and dependence are alien to him. "To live by lies, deceit and begging is the lot of good-for-nothing rogues. Put your faith in the Lord, and trust in your own powers and abilities. Even the hardest earth will yield good crops to honest and selfless toil." [Abai, 2005, 86]. Abai was convinced that only thanks to work a person will achieve moral perfection, and believed that a respectful attitude to work is necessary: "Some Kazakh sayings merit attention and some do not, for they do not carry anything divine or human in them. The Kazakhs say: "If you live in need, forget your shame". Cursed be the life that knows no shame! But if the proverb counsels one not to shun any hard work, however lowly, there is nothing shameful in such work. An upright man should earn his bread honestly, not live on alms or sit back in indolence. "A clever fellow can set even the snow on fire", "You can get anything, if you know how to ask". These are words condemned by God! Is it not better to get riches from the earth by the sweat of your brow rather than rely on cunning and beg

for crumbs from another man's table?" [Abai, 2005, 134].

An important condition in achieving the ideal is knowledge and thinking, which enable a person to analyze not only natural phenomena, but also social life. In the process of cognitive and practical activity, a person gets rid of vices, since they are a product of ignorance and ignorance, grows spiritually, develops a life worthy for a person.

According to Abai, knowledge precedes action. Actions, however, not only eliminate vices, but also their causes, and affirm the opposite virtue of vice. The goal, the meaning of human existence can really be achieved when a person comprehends knowledge, science, realizes the accumulated intellectual potential in labor activity: "The strength of a person believed, Abai, lies in his mind and knowledge..." [Abai, 1993, 218]. That is why, in his creative activity, he paid special attention to the problems of upbringing and education of the younger generation.

Unlike oriental thinkers, the perfect man of Abai is a completely earthly man. The only difference is that he is improving, working on himself, and in comparison with ordinary people he has the advantage that he is subject to inspiration, is open to spirituality and is able to understand the word of God.

"A perfect man" - ("tolyk adam") of Abai is a highly moral, spiritual person who combines the earthly, material and divine. "You should know, the path of the Most High is infinite, and it is given to no to traverse it to the end. He who is resolved to follow this path is considered a true Muslim" [Abai, 2005, 162].

It was the absolutely wise, Abai believes, "Such men know neither sleep nor repose nor diversions; they persevere in a tireless quest for discoveries that might be useful to humankind. They have given man electricity, the power of lightning, they have learnt to communicate with one another over immense distances, they have compelled fire and water to perform colossal work that even thousands of men cannot do. They improve the human mind, they teach us to distinguish good from evil, and we are certainly indebted to them for many things". [Abai, 2005, 161].

The individual becomes a "perfect man" thanks to his own systematic self-education and self-development. The one who builds up and develops his wisdom, doing it incessantly, that perfect person, the poet calls: "If I am called a man, How can I be a dark ignoramus?" [Abai, 1961, 474].

What function is assigned to a perfect person, and how does he differ from others? First of all, he is the manifestation of God on earth. Each person potentially contains the ability to reflect divine attributes.

If a person fully reflects the divine essence (and, as you know, God cannot be known in himself), then to know Him it is necessary to rise to the sight of God as the only reality. The knowledge of a person is due to the fact that his soul is enlightened in the world of God, thus it gets acquainted with the essence of truly existing. Thus, the main goal of a perfect person is to know himself.

If we return from the Abai era to the modern situation, then in general conceptual terms, cultural identity is broader than self-identification. It includes ethnic (determining which culture a given individual belongs to - for example, Kazakh, Russian, German); civilizational (to which culture - for example, eastern or western - it is attributed); socio-political (to which culture the individual belongs - Soviet or market), etc. But, perhaps, the concept of identity and the corresponding problem are most often encountered in research on ethnology, since the most acute problem of all 19 problems concerning forms of identity is the problem of ethnicity, or ethnic identity [Orynbekov, 1994, 207].

“As you know, ethnic identity is based on factors perceived at the personal level (language, traditions and cultural memory, territory, etc.). As for the national identity, it is largely based on ideas about civilizational development, economic resources, society, cultural and historical past.

These components of identity do not contradict each other. But in order for them to be combined, the state must build a system of relations based on mutual understanding and trust, on the recognition of the rights and interests of “others”, i.e. to create the backbone of a multicultural society” [Frank, 1992, 65].

Another aspect of the problem, the other side of it, cannot be ignored. It lies in the fact that the concept of cultural identity is very often, almost as a rule, mixed with identities of a different kind. National (ethnic) identification is the identification of oneself with a certain language, cultural characteristics, including religion, traditions, history, Fatherland. These “five truths” allow a person to answer the question “Who are you?”.

The inappropriateness of mixing these concepts is clearly visible in the example of the absolutization of the principle of cultural pluralism, which can lead to an exacerbation of those negative trends that clearly run counter to state policy aimed at national consolidation on the scale of the entire Kazakh society. The fact is that the culture of an ethnos ensures not only its integration and stability: the elements of this culture also have another side, since they also perform ethnodifferentiating functions, i.e. become the basis for distinguishing between “we” and “they”. For each ethnic group, as G. Narbekova justly points out, the existence of other ethnic groups is an external phenomenon that differs not only in the content of life, but also due to the dissimilarity of the cultural image. The principle of self-determination of cultural communities cannot serve as an unconditional criterion in an approach to cultural problems, since it turns out to be dependent on other factors of social life. The independence of cultures of different communities is always complemented by their interconnection and interaction either on the basis of a common spiritual life, or through an established system of mutual understanding and trust [Narbekova, 2004, 271].

In addition to the thought about the illegitimacy of identifying cultural identity with other types of identity, especially with ethno-national identity, one can cite a very accurate statement by G. Shalabayeva: “...identity with oneself would never have grown into a complex problem if a person of a certain ethnic group meant a

simple adherence to the characteristics and properties of his nature. Finding oneself turns into a problem due to the specifics of the very way of human existence” [Shalabayeva, 1995, 213].

Of course, different types of identity in one way or another intersect, interact, overlap each other in the space of society. There is a complex interweaving of them, as a result of which such phenomena as, for example, “ethno-confessionalism” arise, when ethnicity is mechanically equated with confessional, or “ethno-cultural identity”, as in the case we are considering.

In this sense, one cannot but agree that “for a number of reasons, it is ethnicity that has been, over the past ten years, a socially universal certainty and a universally significant context of personality self-identification in our society” [Kurganskaya, 2003, 61].

CONCLUSION

Yet self-identification “Becoming a human” is a deeper and different concept than identity, we may say, cultural, or national, or religious, or political, or civic. Cultural identity, we emphasize this once again, is a broader concept and a more flexible phenomenon. One can ask the question which culture I belong to - old or new, and this will not be a question, for example, about national identity. You can ask which culture I should fit into: Western or Eastern, and this will not be fully a question of civil identity. Speaking about a person's self-identification, one can evaluate it in two ways: 1) self-identification is a consequence of human activity and 2) self-identification is a consequence of culture. In other words, the question arises of where does the status of self-identification, respectively, its crisis come from - from within the culture itself as a social phenomenon or from within the human personality?

To this, most likely, the following answer should be given: in the nearest, direct way, the crisis of identity arises from culture. Culture is changing - and in this transformation process a person is able to lose himself in his usual cultural self-measurement. But ultimately, or in the essential sense, the crisis of identity must be attributed to the person himself. And the mechanism here is quite simple: a person is never satisfied either in his egoism or in his creative searches, and he always needs something new, he must constantly prove that he is a human being, “To be a human” (Abai). However, when something new appears, the person is again dissatisfied. Consequently, it is again not identical to the present culture, and that, in turn, is thus not identical within itself.

It is important to emphasize that in the second case a double problem arises: an individual can lose touch with his ethnic culture, but not lose touch with the culture in which he was born or which he chose as “his”. Conversely, the paradoxes of identification are, therefore, resolved in such a way that identification should be made only in relation to the high value patterns of internal and external culture. The identification specimen must be axiologically sound. As V. Hesle, only by identifying with values that have nothing to do with selfish interest, the “I” becomes self-confident and acquires a sense of dignity [Hesle, 1994, 112-123].

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